

THE USE OF INPUT WORDS WHICH ENTERED THE UZBEK LANGUAGE FROM ENGLISH

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Annotation, *The article discusses various social aspects of foreign loan words in the Uzbek language. It is analyzed as English words appeared in the Uzbek language in different historical periods and under different socio-cultural circumstances, and also attention is paid to the degree of adaptation of foreign loan words in the Uzbek language. The article also discusses the morphological and lexical changes in foreign loan words.*

Keywords: *social aspects of foreign words, level of adaptation, morphological and lexical changes.*

Foreign language elements into the current Uzbek language causes a number of problems within the language. Many linguists view language as a "living organism" that has an internal and external influence on the development of society in the socio-political, economic and spiritual spheres. There is constant interaction between different languages, as a result of which languages are filled with acquired words, their vocabulary is enriched. Learning foreign words is a natural process of development and enrichment of any language, including the Uzbek language. Foreign words proves the lexical power of the "acquired" language, as new words obey its grammatical norms. The Uzbek language is an example of a language that assimilates and enriches foreign words under the influence of various political, economic and socio-historical processes throughout its existence. The topic of learning foreign languages is relevant at the current stage of political, economic and social development of the current Uzbek society. This article discusses the cultural and social aspects of learning foreign words in the Uzbek language. Reasons for foreign words in the Uzbek language. In the linguistic encyclopedic dictionary you can find the following definition:(Volume 5, Issue 10, 2019)

"Acquisition is an element of a foreign language (word, morpheme, syntactic structure, etc.) that is transferred from one language to another as a result of language contacts, as well as the process of transferring elements of one language to another" [1]. O. S. Akhmanova understands borrowing as "referring to the lexical fund of other languages to express new concepts, further differentiate existing ones, and define previously unknown objects." D.E.Rosenthal defined adopted words as a natural result of the establishment of economic, political and cultural relations between peoples, the words that denote them enter the language with reality and concepts [3]. and the need to define locations. The degree of influence of one language on another language in their interaction depends not only on the level of development of material and spiritual culture, the presence or absence of written and literary traditions, etc. The closest language ties occur in the context of ethnic bilingualism. L.P. Krysin explains: "In order for a word to be acquired from a foreign language and adapted to a new language, it is necessary for the members of the receiving society to know more or less the transmitting language. They must be at least partially bilingual, otherwise they will not understand the meaning of the word. [4]. N. N. Amosova [5, p. 220]

suggests distinguishing the following types of assimilation: 1) complete assimilations (words that have remained equivalent in the new language environment or have undergone certain phonetic and grammatical changes during assimilation); 2) relative acquisitions (foreign words that have lost their semantic connection with their prototypes in the original language during the development of the adopted language); 3) words created in their own language from foreign language morphemes; 4) words of local color (used only in an appropriate ethnographic or historical context). According to most linguists, according to the level of assimilation, they can be classified as follows: local figurative appropriations, that is, words that are completely imperceptible as an element of a foreign language, and special expressions that are weakly assimilated lexical words in a foreign language, is limited. in their use, mainly ethnographic or historical communication.

And as noted by L.P. Krysin [4], the vocabulary of a foreign language can be divided into several groups that differ significantly stylistically according to the degree of assimilation:

1) a dictionary of a foreign language with an unlimited scope of use in the modern Russian language: a) words that have lost signs of non-Russian origin (station, combine, tractor, patio); b) words that are not specific to the Uzbek language and retain some external signs of consonants (jaz, parda); non-Uzbek suffixes (student, technical school, director); non-Uzbek prefixes (ether, antibiotics); such borrowed words are stylistically combined with the original Russian vocabulary; c) the so-called Europeanisms or internationalisms (party, development), which are widely used in the fields of science, politics, culture, art, known not only in the Uzbek language, but also in other European languages;

2) foreign language terms that often do not have synonyms (slang, rhyme, phoneme). But there are also foreign language terms that have Russian and Old Slavic synonyms (import - import, evolution - development, communique - message). The classification of borrowings according to the degree of adaptation is legitimate with a synchronic approach to vocabulary; for each subsequent period, such a classification becomes anachronistic. Acquisition of words borrowed by a language is a complex diachronic process, because the lexical system of any language is constantly changing. Different stages of social development are characterized by the actualization of certain thematic groups of the dictionary. For example, political vocabulary, military, nuclear, space, mining, and geology expand during certain periods.

Exoticism has a special place among appropriation. They are used, for example, to describe people's customs, rituals, religion, lifestyle, etc. These include ethnicity, names of banknotes, types of clothing, food, and more. Some scientists do not include them in the number of borrowings, because they do not belong to the language system in use and do not work in it in a strong connection with the lexical and grammatical structure of these language units. In the process of studying loans from Western countries, we analyzed the following evidence. Under the influence of economic and social relations with Germany and the Netherlands, the Uzbek language was enriched with words such as sandwich (belegtes Brot), accountant (Buchhalter), fireworks (Feuerwerk), fair (Jahrmarkt), chair (Stuhl), schnitzel (. . Schnitzel) and others. As a result of interest in the German military system, military terms appeared in Uzbek: aiguillettes (Achselechnur), guard house (Hauptwache), howitzer (Haubitze), corporal (Gefreite). Another external reason for borrowing is to designate a certain object or concept using a new word. For example, the French word porter has replaced the hotel manager on duty, and the English word jam has replaced the thick jam sign. Internal and external causes of embezzlement are interrelated.

The socially determined demand for the specialization of concepts is facilitated by the tendency of language to differentiate linguistic means more clearly according to meaning. As a result, pairs of words appeared in the Uzbek language that are similar in meaning, but not always synonymous: reportage and news, total and universal, hobby and hobby, etc. In addition, dictionaries of loanwords, which quickly respond to all changes and provide the correct meaning and small information about a particular word, can help. But in modern Uzbek, their number is very limited. Dictionaries of idioms are very useful for didactic purposes.

Analyzing the existing literature and sources on the problem of self-determination, we can draw the following conclusions:

1. Acquisition is a universal, multifaceted and complex process, in which the acquired word is adapted to the phonetic and spelling system of the acquired language, as well as subordinated to its grammatical structure, added to the acquired word must take into account all the conditions listed. This means phonetic, spelling and grammatical adaptations.

2. Acquisitions can be direct and indirect, early and late, but the main part of the vocabulary in the Uzbek language is acquired through the Russian language. That's why all Germans have mastered the words of the 19th and 20th centuries. entered the Uzbek language through the Russian language. In the first years of research, the acquired lexical layers² were studied only through the Russian language, including their linguistic foundations.

3. Foreign words from English come from two sources: loan words that entered the Uzbek language through the Russian language, and local words that passed through connections between the German and English languages. At present (21st century), direct communication in Uzbek language is established for German, English, American, French and Uzbek cooperation in technology, economy, science and other fields of national economy. Especially with Germany. Car factories and other public facilities were built.

4. The vocabulary acquired during the transition from one language to another has been adapted to the Uzbek language at the current stage. We studied them and published works for this purpose.

REFERENCES

1. Linguistic encyclopedic dictionary / ch. ed. V. N. Yartseva. M.: Sov. Encycl., 1990. 682 p.
2. Akhmanova O. S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. M.: USSR. 2004. 569 p.
3. Rosenthal D. E., Telenkova M. A. Dictionary-reference of linguistic terms. M.: Enlightenment. 1976. 543 p.
4. Krysin L.P. Development of the vocabulary of the modern Russian language. M.: 1965. B. 117-137.
5. Amosova N. N. Etymological foundations of the modern English dictionary. M., 1956. 218 p.
6. Cherepanova A.V. Borrowing in Russian speech and their use among young people. (No. 33-1, pp. 205-209).